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LEVEL OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF TEACHERS AT COLÉGIO ESTADUAL DA POLÍCIA MILITARY DE GOIÁS – CALDAS NOVAS - GO

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ABSTRACT

Through the development of Emotional Intelligence (EQ) in teachers, they favor the improvement in the teaching-learning process and in interpersonal relationships.